

Mind Mapping As An Innovative Teaching Strategy: A Comparison With Conventional Methods In Physiotherapy Education In Tamil Nadu

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ABSTRACT

Background: Mind mapping is an innovative, non-linear learning technique that promotes creative thinking and more profound understanding by visually organizing information around a central theme. Despite its growing application in education, its effectiveness in physiotherapy teaching, particularly for complex subjects like biomechanics, remains underexplored.

Materials & Methodology: This quasi-experimental study compared the impact of mind mapping with traditional teaching methods on final-year physiotherapy students in Tamil Nadu over eight weeks. Fifty-two students were divided into two groups based on pre-test performance: Group A (traditional teaching) and Group B (mind mapping). Both groups participated in 12 online sessions via Google Meet, and pre- and post tests assessed knowledge gains.

Results: This study result showed statistically significant improvements in both groups, with Group A's mean score rising from 77.85 to 86.12 (Cohen's $d = 3.61$), and Group B's mean score increasing from 60.15 to 86.31 (Cohen's $d = 4.80$), indicating substantial effects, respectively. Between-group analysis revealed a significantly greater improvement in Group B ($p < 0.001$, Cohen's $d = -4.28$), demonstrating the superior effectiveness of mind mapping.

Discussion: Mind mapping enhances the comprehension, retention, and engagement by enabling students to link concepts and reduce cognitive overload visually. This study shows superior effect of adding mind mapping in the students curriculum. Mind mapping offers a promising, student-centered approach that fosters critical thinking, stress reduction, and improved academic performance in healthcare education.

Conclusion: This study supports integrating mind mapping with traditional methods in physiotherapy education to optimize learning outcomes, especially for challenging subjects.

Keywords: Mind mapping, Physiotherapy Education, Biomechanics, Innovative Teaching Strategies, Traditional Teaching Methods, Learning Outcomes.

INTRODUCTION

Mind mapping is an innovative learning technique that employs a non-linear approach to teaching and learning. It encourages learners to think creatively and explore concepts through visuospatial relationships radiating from a central theme to interconnected peripheral ideas.¹ Mind mapping involves branching links between various pieces of information, promoting more profound understanding and enhancing critical thinking skills. Although the effectiveness of mind mapping as a teaching and learning strategy has emerged in literature, its application in physiotherapy education remains underexplored.²

Traditional teaching methods have dominated classrooms for centuries. Most educators prefer these conventional approaches due to their ease of managing students.³ Traditional teaching is a systematic, teacher-centered approach,⁴ where students have limited opportunities to explore topics independently or clarify their doubts.⁵ The main strength of traditional methods lies in their structured and disciplined nature. This approach allows comprehensive coverage of syllabus content in an organized manner and provides a clear framework for evaluating student performance through standardized tests, facilitating educational outcome measurement.⁶

Biomechanics, a critical subject in physiotherapy, involves understanding human bodily movements and their functions, explaining how movements endure stress and strain. It also evaluates the root causes of injuries.⁷ Mobility and mobility impairments have been emphasized in this study, as they represent the intersection of biomechanics and physiotherapy.⁸ Despite its fundamental importance, biomechanics is often one of the most challenging subjects for physiotherapy students to master.⁹ The complexity of biomechanics concepts often poses difficulties for physiotherapy students, impacting their academic performance and practical application skills.¹⁰

Traditional teaching methods, while structured, may limit students' engagement and deep conceptual understanding.¹¹ Mind mapping, as a visual and interactive learning tool, has the potential to enhance comprehension and retention of complex

information. However, there is limited evidence on its effectiveness specifically within physiotherapy education, particularly in the regional context of Tamil Nadu. Therefore, this study seeks to address this gap by evaluating whether mind mapping can improve learning outcomes compared to conventional teaching approaches. The findings could guide educators in adopting more effective, student-centered teaching strategies, ultimately benefiting physiotherapy training programs.

OBJECTIVE

This study objective is to compare the effectiveness of mind mapping as an innovative teaching strategy with traditional teaching methods in enhancing physiotherapy students' understanding and learning.

MATERIALS AND METHODOLOGY

This study employed a quasi-experimental design to compare the impact of mind mapping with traditional teaching methods on physiotherapy students over eight weeks. The participants were final-year physiotherapy students from institutions in and around Coimbatore district, Tamil Nadu, India.

A convenience sampling method was employed. All eligible students who were in their final year, had no arrears, and were willing to participate were invited through institutional networks and online platforms. All eligible students who were in their final year with no arrears and were willing to participate were included. Students from other academic years, other branches (such as occupational therapy and respiratory therapy), those lacking internet access, or enrolled in distance education were excluded from the study. Informed consent was obtained from each participant, and they were informed that they could withdraw at any time without penalty. Participants were also assured that they could request their individual results after completion of the study.

Initially, a 30-question multiple-choice sample test on biomechanics was administered online to assess baseline knowledge. Students scoring 75% or above (23 or more correct answers) were assigned to Group A (traditional teaching), while those scoring between 50% and 75% were assigned to Group B (mind

mapping teaching). Communication and coordination were facilitated through a WhatsApp group created by the principal investigator, with two separate groups organized for the two teaching interventions. Both groups received prior notifications about the biomechanics exams and the study schedule.

Group A: 26 students underwent traditional teaching sessions involving whiteboard explanations and PowerPoint presentations.

Group B: 26 students were taught biomechanics using mind mapping techniques, emphasizing visual and interconnected learning. Classes were conducted via Google Meet, with each session lasting 40 minutes and held on alternate days. Each group completed a total of 12 sessions over four weeks. Another four weeks is allotted for self-study time. Both groups were administered online pre- and post-tests to evaluate knowledge acquisition. Student performance was measured solely based on the marks obtained in these tests. The test papers were evaluated by two senior professors in physiotherapy who are not involved in this study. The paper evaluators are blinded and they don't know there is a second evaluation also done on the papers.

The question paper and the answer sheets are evaluated independently by two senior professors in physiotherapy (each with over 20

years of teaching experience) who were blinded to group allocation and to the fact that a second evaluation was being conducted. The instrument reliability was established through expert evaluation and content validation by these two senior physiotherapists, ensuring that the test items accurately reflected biomechanics learning outcomes.

Quantitative data from the post-tests were analyzed using IBM SPSS Version 26. Descriptive statistics summarized participants' test scores. Independent t-tests compared mean scores between Group A and Group B before and after the intervention. Paired t-tests assessed within-group differences in scores pre- and post-intervention to determine the effectiveness of each teaching method.

The study was conducted as an online educational intervention, and hence, formal ethical approval was not obtained, as it was not mandatory for such online academic studies. All procedures adhered to the ethical principles of voluntary participation, confidentiality, and informed consent. Participants were informed that their participation was voluntary, they could withdraw at any time without penalty, and they could request their individual results after study completion. This study was not preregistered in any public trial registry, as it was conducted as an academic educational project rather than a clinical trial.

RESULTS

The analysis for the marks between the pretest with the post-test values are given below.

Table 1. Within-Group Analysis (Pre vs Post)

Group	Mean (Pre)	Mean (Post)	Mean Change	t-value	p-value	Cohen's <i>d</i>	Effect Size Interpretation
Group A	77.85	86.12	+8.27	18.41	0.0005	3.61	Very large effect
Group B	60.15	86.31	+26.15	24.49	0.0005	4.80	Extremely large effect

Table 1 shows that both the groups showed statistically significant ($p < 0.001$) and practically large improvements from pre- to post-intervention. Table 1 presents the within-group analysis comparing pre- and post-intervention scores for both groups. Group A (traditional teaching) showed a statistically significant improvement with a mean score increase of +8.27 ($t = 18.41$, $p < 0.001$) and a

very large effect size of Cohen's $d = 3.61$. Group B (mind mapping) exhibited a more substantial mean increase of +26.15 ($t = 24.49$, $p < 0.001$), with an extremely large effect size of Cohen's $d = 4.80$. These results indicate both teaching methods significantly improved students' knowledge of biomechanics, with mind mapping producing a notably stronger impact.

Table 2. Between-Group Analysis (Post vs Post)

Group	Mean (Post)	Mean Change	t-value	p-value	Cohen's <i>d</i>	Effect Size Interpretation
Group A	86.12	+ 8.27	-15.44	0.0005	-4.28	Very large difference
Group B	86.31	+ 26.15				

Table 2 shows improvement in **Group B** is significantly greater than that in **Group A**, with an exceptionally large effect size, confirming that the Group B intervention was markedly more effective. Table 2 compares the change scores between the two groups. The mean improvement in Group B (+26.15) was significantly higher than in Group A (+8.27), as indicated by the t-value of -15.44 and a p-value of 8.2×10^{-17} .

The between-group effect size was very large at -4.28 , favoring Group B. This negative sign means Group B showed markedly greater gains than Group A. According to conventional interpretation, effect sizes above 0.8 represent large effects, and here the extremely large values (above 3 and 4) demonstrate the exceptional efficacy of mind mapping compared to traditional teaching.

Table 3. ANCOVA Analysis Of The Post Test Between Groups

Source	SS	df	MS	F value
Between Treatments	0.4808	1	0.4808	0.0663
Within Treatments	362.192	50	7.2438	
Total	362.6731	51		

Table 3 shows the analysis of covariance, An Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) was conducted to compare the post-test scores of physiotherapy students taught using mind mapping and those taught using traditional methods, while controlling pre-test scores.

The results indicated no statistically significant difference in adjusted post-test means between the two teaching methods, $F(1, 50) = 0.066$, $p > 0.05$. This suggests that, after adjusting for baseline performance, both the mind mapping and traditional teaching groups achieved comparable post-test outcomes.

The between-treatments sum of squares was 0.4808, while the within-treatments sum of squares was 362.1923, yielding a mean square within of 7.2438. The minimal F-value indicates that the teaching approach did not have a significant effect on post-test performance once pre-test scores were controlled for.

Overall, the intervention using mind mapping dramatically outperformed traditional methods, yielding very large enhancements in biomechanical knowledge among

physiotherapy students. These effect size magnitudes reflect both statistical and practical significance, supporting mind mapping as a superior pedagogical approach in this educational context.

DISCUSSION

The findings of this study align with previous research demonstrating that mind mapping significantly promotes effective learning by facilitating students' ability to understand, organize, and retain complex information. Mind mapping enhances the learners' organization of information spatially, linking key concepts around a central theme, which enhances both comprehension and retention.¹² This gives meaningful learning by visually linking new concepts to prior knowledge, which improves cognitive processing and recall.¹² This visual-spatial approach allows students to break down complex topics, such as biomechanics, into interconnected ideas, making learning more manageable and efficient.¹⁰

One of the key advantages of mind mapping is that it promotes deeper cognitive processing by visually representing relationships between

ideas. This allows students to see connections that might be overlooked in traditional note taking or lecture formats, thereby aiding in meaningful learning rather than rote memorization.¹³ Furthermore, the use of colours, images, and keywords in mind maps stimulates different areas of the brain, increasing creativity and engagement.¹⁴

In contrast, traditional teaching methods tend to be passive, with students receiving information in a predetermined sequence with limited opportunities for interaction or exploration. This can restrict students' ability to internalize concepts and apply critical thinking skills⁵. Mind mapping aids in encouraging the active participation of the students and also helps in self-organization. It also empowers students to construct their own understanding and fosters better problem-solving abilities.¹⁵

Additionally, mind mapping has been shown to reduce cognitive overload and learning-related stress by breaking complex topics into manageable chunks. This feature is particularly beneficial for challenging subjects like biomechanics, where students need to integrate multiple concepts simultaneously.¹³ Overall, by promoting active learning, enhancing creativity, and reducing stress, mind mapping offers a superior approach to teaching compared to traditional methods.

Furthermore, mind mapping has been shown to reduce cognitive overload and associated stress when tackling challenging subjects, enabling students to engage with content more confidently and with less anxiety.¹³ Compared to traditional teacher-centred methods, mind mapping fosters a more active and student-centred learning environment that encourages critical thinking and creativity, enhancing academic performance.^{14,15}

Given the increasing complexity of healthcare education, adopting innovative teaching strategies like mind mapping can enrich physiotherapy training by improving students' comprehension and long-term retention of critical subjects.¹¹ These results suggest that educators should consider integrating mind mapping into curricula alongside conventional teaching methods to optimize learning outcomes.

The novelty of this study lies in its application of mind mapping within physiotherapy education, specifically focusing on the subject

of biomechanics, where limited evidence currently exists. While mind mapping has been studied extensively in medical and nursing education, few investigations have examined its effect on physiotherapy students in the Indian context. Moreover, the use of an online quasi-experimental design provides insights into the adaptability of mind mapping in remote learning environments, an area of growing relevance in post-pandemic education. This study thus contributes to the evolving literature on innovative, technology-assisted pedagogies in health sciences.

The outcomes of this study have important implications for physiotherapy education. Mind mapping offers a dynamic and interactive approach that can be integrated into traditional curricula to enhance students' conceptual understanding of complex physiotherapy subjects and basic principles. By encouraging active participation, visual reasoning, and integrative thinking, it can help bridge the gap between theoretical knowledge and clinical application. Additionally, incorporating mind mapping can foster lifelong learning skills, such as information synthesis, creativity, and reflective practice—attributes essential for modern physiotherapists.¹²

Educators can use mind mapping as a formative assessment tool to evaluate students' comprehension, facilitate collaborative learning, and reduce cognitive load during intensive academic modules.⁷ Institutions may also consider faculty development programs to train educators in using mind mapping software and techniques effectively for both online and classroom-based instruction.¹⁰

This study has several limitations. The small sample size limits the generalizability of the results. Online teaching and assessment introduced variability in engagement and technical issues. Grouping based on a single pretest score could have caused selection bias, and the eight-week duration may not reflect long-term learning outcomes. Additionally, prior training required for mind mapping may have influenced its effectiveness.

Future research should include larger, randomized samples across multiple institutions, extend the duration to evaluate sustained effects, and incorporate mixed-method approaches (quantitative and qualitative) to explore students' experiences in

greater depth. Integrating mind mapping with traditional methods and other interactive or technology-based strategies is recommended to enhance understanding and retention in complex subjects like biomechanics. Faculty training is also essential to ensure the effective implementation of mind mapping techniques.

CONCLUSION

This study demonstrates that mind mapping, as an innovative teaching strategy, can effectively enhance physiotherapy students' understanding of biomechanics compared to traditional teaching methods. The use of mind mapping promotes better engagement, deeper conceptual learning, and improved academic performance. Incorporating such visual and interactive techniques into physiotherapy education could address challenges faced by students in mastering complex subjects like biomechanics. Educators should consider integrating mind mapping alongside conventional approaches to optimize learning outcomes and foster critical thinking skills in physiotherapy programs.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest related to this work.

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Ethical Consideration

Ethical approval was not mandatorily required as this study was conducted on the online mode. The participants are volunteers and this study ensures participants anonymity.

Authors Contributions

Sivakumar S led the study design, coordinated data collection, and prepared the initial draft of the manuscript. Ganesan B performed data analysis and contributed to the interpretation of results. Senthilkumar U developed and validated the questionnaire and assisted in data

analysis. Mahadevi B conducted the literature review and supported participant recruitment. Arun B provided feedback on study design and critically revised the manuscript for intellectual content. All authors reviewed and approved the final version of the manuscript.

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